

MDMC
Master in Data Management
and Curation

MASTER IN DATA MANAGEMENT AND
CURATION

FAIR-by-Design Real-Time Data Pipeline for Hydrogen Digital Twins

Supervisor(s):

Prof. Gianluigi Rozza
Dr. Mariarita de Luca

Candidate:

Valentin Eric Brice Nkana Ngan

2025–2026

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

This course has been funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU within the projects:

- *NFFA-DI cod. IR0000015 - Missione 4, “Istruzione e Ricerca” – Componente 2, “Dalla ricerca all’impresa” – Linea di investimento 3.1, “Fondo per la realizzazione di un sistema integrato di infrastrutture di ricerca e innovazione” – Azione 3.1.1, “Creazione di nuove IR o potenziamento di quelle esistenti che concorrono agli obiettivi di Eccellenza Scientifica di Horizon Europee costituzione di reti” (CUP B53C22004310006)*

[NFFA-DI: Nano Foundries Fine Analysis - Digital Infrastructure](#)

- *EFC cod. SSU2024 – 00002 - Missione 4, “Istruzione e Ricerca” – Componente 1, “Potenziamento dell’offerta dei servizi all’istruzione: dagli asili nido all’ università” – Linea di investimento 3.4, “Didattica e competenze universitarie avanzate” – Sub-Investimento, “Rafforzamento delle scuole universitarie superiori” (CUP G97G24000100007)*

[EFC: Educating Future Citizen](#)

nffa-di

Author's Declaration

I, Valentin Eric Brice Nkana Ngan, declare that this thesis entitled, 'Real-Time Sensor Data Ingestion and Quality Assurance for Hydrogen Digital Twins: A FAIR Engineering Approach' and the work presented therein are my own.

I certify that:

- This work was performed wholly or principally during MDMC internship in the Laboratory of Data Engineering (LADE) in Area Science Park in collaboration with SISSA.
- If any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have relied on the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where the thesis is based on work I have done in collaboration with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I contributed.
 - I acknowledge the use of Claude, ChatGPT, and DeepSeek to identify improvements in the writing style and coding.
 - I acknowledge the use of the Bibliography as a source of information to create materials that will be used in my own words.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always cited. Except for such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all major sources of help.

"Outside their particular area of expertise, scientists are just as dumb as the next person."

Richard P. Feynman

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to God the creator of the heaven and earth, the Father, our Lord Jesus Christ, for granting me the opportunity to participate in this program and for giving me the strength to successfully complete it.

I would also like to sincerely thank SISSA for awarding me the fellowship that made it possible for me to pursue this Master's program.

I would also like to express my sincere gratitude to Prof. Gianluigi Rozza for his supervision and continuous support throughout this program and since our first meeting.

In addition, I would like to sincerely thank Dr. Mariarita de Luca for supervising this thesis, for providing the initial materials for this work, and for her availability for discussions and willingness to share her knowledge.

I would also like to thank all the lecturers of this program for their engaging lectures, for the knowledge they generously shared, and for the many fruitful discussions.

My greatest debt in attending this program is to my wife Armelle and my daughters Gabriella, Emmanuelle, and Raphaele for surrounding me with unconditional love, support, and a peaceful environment that made this possible.

Finally, I wish to thank my classmates Enrico, Luis, Roberta, Sandeep, Leslie, Ruth, Smritirekha, Ana, Jacopo, Emmanuel, and Micol for the stimulating and fruitful exchanges we enjoyed over the course of the program.

Abstract

Hydrogen energy is a versatile energy carrier, increasingly recognized for its role in a sustainable energy future due to its high energy density and compatibility with existing gas infrastructure. Digital Twin (DT) technology has emerged as a pivotal cyber-physical tool for integrating hydrogen energy into modern energy systems, enabling virtual modelling, predictive analysis, and system optimization across the full production-storage-utilization chain.

The H2SmartLab project was conceived to instantiate this vision: a research infrastructure that smartly integrates renewable hydrogen production, storage, and utilization with advanced monitoring and failure prediction, underpinned by a DT platform called Hydor. However, a critical gap remains between the physical laboratory, where raw experimental data is generated, and the DT layer that must consume it in real time. Without a robust, validated data pipeline, the DT cannot operate reliably or reproducibly.

This thesis addresses that gap by designing and implementing a real-time, event-driven data pipeline built on Apache Kafka, a three-stage data quality validation layer, and a time-series storage system using QuestDB. A FastAPI synchronization layer provides the interface between the physical laboratory and the Hydor DT platform, offering authenticated, FAIR-aligned data access. The implemented system achieves sub-second ingestion latency, automated anomaly detection via per-record quality validation, and full FAIR4RS software compliance, demonstrating a reproducible architecture for monitoring hydrogen and broader industrial infrastructure.

Keywords— FAIR principles, Digital Twins, FAIR workflow, hydrogen energy, real-time data pipeline, Apache Kafka, QuestDB, FastAPI, data quality, interoperability, FAIR4RS, research data management

Contents

1	Introduction	10
1.1	The H2SmartLab Research Infrastructure	10
1.2	Problem Statement	11
1.3	Research Objectives	12
1.4	Methodology Overview	12
1.5	Related Work	13
1.6	Scientific Contributions	13
1.7	Thesis Structure	14
2	System Architecture	15
2.1	Architecture	15
2.1.1	Core Components	16
2.1.2	Relevance to Real-Time Data Pipelines	17
2.2	Data Quality	17
2.2.1	Accuracy	18
2.2.2	Completeness	19
2.2.3	Consistency	19
2.2.4	Timeliness	19
2.3	Data Storage	20
2.3.1	Time-Series Databases	20
2.3.2	Data Ingestion Format	22
3	FAIR in digital twins	24
3.1	DT in H2SmartLab	24
3.2	Findability	25
3.3	Accessibility	27
3.4	Interoperability	27
3.5	Reusability	28
4	Implementation	30
4.1	FAIR Principles for Research Software	30
4.2	Findability	30
4.2.1	F1 – Globally unique and persistent identifier.	31
4.2.2	F2 – Rich metadata.	31
4.2.3	F3 – Metadata explicitly includes the software identifier	31
4.2.4	F4 – Searchable and indexed metadata.	32
4.3	Accessibility	32
4.3.1	Software Access	32
4.3.2	Authentication and Access Control	32

4.4	Interoperability	33
4.4.1	Storage Layer	33
4.4.2	FastAPI Routing	33
4.5	Reusability	34
4.5.1	Deployment Environment	34
4.5.2	Data Quality Layer	35
4.5.3	Provenance and Attribution	36
4.6	Physics Simulation Layer	36
4.6.1	Design Rationale	36
4.6.2	Sub-model Structure	38
4.6.3	Streaming Interface	38
5	Conclusion	40

List of Figures

2.1	Overview of the proposed architecture	15
2.2	Apache Kafka Architecture [1]	16
2.3	Data quality dimensions [2]	18
3.1	Elements of the digital twin ecosystem. Information flows bidirectionally between the virtual representation and physical counterpart. These information flows may be through automated processes, human-driven processes, or a combination of the two. [3]	25
3.2	FAIR guiding principles as outlined by Wilkinson et al. 2016 [4]	26
4.1	FAIR4RS Principles [5].	31

List of Tables

2.1	Summary of Data Quality Dimensions and Metrics for Industrial Sensor Data. Adapted from [6]	21
2.2	Structure of Kafka telemetry messages from fuel cell sensors.	22
3.1	FAIR principles applied in the H2SmartLab data platform, mapped to the sub-principles of Wilkinson et al. [7]. Cells marked “future work” identify areas where the current architecture only partially satisfies the relevant FAIR criterion.	29
4.1	Software components, access points, and identifiers.	32
4.2	FastAPI router summary.	34
4.3	Docker Compose services and their exposed ports.	34
4.4	Mapping of FAIR4RS Principles [5] to implementation choices.	37
4.5	Physics simulator sub-models and their calibration sources.	38

Chapter 1

Introduction

The global energy system is undergoing a profound structural transformation. Driven by accelerating climate commitments, rapid electrification across industrial and residential sectors, and a projected 49% rise in global electricity production by 2040 [8]. The need to decarbonize energy supply has never been greater. Yet abundance of renewable capacity alone is insufficient: the intermittent nature of solar and wind generation, combined with the persistent difficulty of decarbonizing hard-to-abate sectors such as heavy transport and high-temperature industry, demands not only new energy sources but new *systems* for managing, storing, and distributing energy intelligently.

Green hydrogen (hydrogen produced from renewable electricity) has emerged as one of the most strategically significant responses to this challenge [9]. As an energy carrier, it offers high gravimetric (measured by mass or weight) energy density, compatibility with existing gas infrastructure, and the capacity to bridge temporal and geographic mismatches between renewable supply and end-use demand. Its potential spans power-to-gas storage, industrial feedstock substitution, and long-distance heavy transport applications where direct electrification remains either technically or economically impractical [10].

In Italy, the installed renewable energy capacity reached 65,157 MW in 2023 [11], with a further 3 GW added in May 2024 and a total increase of 7.1 GW the year-end [12]. This rapid growth underlines the urgency of developing complementary technologies particularly hydrogen systems capable of absorbing surplus generation and providing dispatchable, carbon-free energy when renewable output is constrained.

1.1 The H2SmartLab Research Infrastructure

The H2SmartLab project was established to develop an integrated research infrastructure spanning the full hydrogen value chain: two different storage technologies are foreseen in H2SmartLab, pressurized storage and Metallic hydrides. A distinguishing feature of the project is its emphasis on *digital intelligence*: the laboratory is conceived not merely as a physical testbed, but as a *cyber-physical system* in which hardware components are continuously mirrored, monitored, and optimized through their digital counterparts. Central to this vision, is the concept of the Digital Twin (DT) — a dynamic virtual representation of a physical asset or process, continuously synchronized with real-world measurements and capable of supporting predictive analysis, fault detection, and scenario simulation. DTs have been increasingly adopted in energy systems research, including applications in electrolyser monitoring, fuel cell diagnostics, and integrated hydrogen networks [13, 14, 15]. However, their efficacy is critically dependent

on the quality and latency of the supporting data infrastructure; indeed, a digital twin can only be as reliable as the data it receives.

To realize this vision, the H2SmartLab infrastructure is organized around two complementary nodes: the physical *H2 Integrated Lab*, and the *Hydor* node. Together, these nodes form a tightly coupled physical-digital ecosystem for hydrogen production, monitoring, and simulation.

The first, *APSU*¹, laboratory, consists of multiple experimental stations where systems for renewable hydrogen production, storage, and utilization are deployed. The hydrogen produced will be certified as green, then the whole electricity required for the hydrogen synthesis comes from the photovoltaic field.

Co-located with *APSU*, the second laboratory, the *MFI*², is dedicated to additional real-time monitoring of operational parameters across the hydrogen value chain. Equipped with a distributed sensor network, the *MFI* captures both the quantity and *quality of data* required for system analysis and optimization, enabling continuous monitoring of production, storage, and utilization processes. The collected data are automatically ingested into a time-series database connected to the local computing infrastructure, ensuring efficient storage and accessibility for downstream processing, and most importantly, providing the continuous data stream necessary to feed the DT. The work presented in this thesis developed the data communication bridge between the physical and the digital component of H2SmartLab.

This data stream is received and processed by the *Hydor* node, which represents the digital counterpart of the infrastructure. *Hydor* is responsible for providing the computational and storage resources required for the development and operation of the DT, integrating high-performance computing (HPC), advanced data management, artificial intelligence (AI), and numerical simulation techniques to enable real-time analysis and scenario evaluation. The computational infrastructure is based on state-of-the-art parallel architectures, including graphics processing units (GPUs), particularly suited for accelerating AI-driven numerical methods, ensuring efficient execution of computationally intensive tasks while minimizing energy consumption. To further reduce computational overhead, advanced methodologies such as Reduced Order Models (ROMs) are employed to lower the complexity of high-fidelity simulations — an important consideration given the large volume of data continuously generated by the H2 Integrated Lab, which must be assimilated into the DT in near real-time. Finally, through a web-based interface, authenticated users can access and interact with the system remotely using lightweight devices, ensuring full integration between the physical and digital components of the infrastructure and enabling a scalable, real-time DT ecosystem.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite significant advances in hydrogen technology and DT methodology, a gap persists at their interface. Physical hydrogen laboratories generate continuous, high-frequency streams of heterogeneous sensor data pressures, temperatures, flow rates, electrochemical signals that must be ingested, validated, and delivered to digital systems with minimal latency and maximum reliability [16, 15]. Existing approaches frequently address data ingestion and storage in isolation, without integrating the data quality assurance, access control, and interoperability mechanisms that scientific and industrial deployments require [17].

¹Analysis of Hydrogen Production

²Measurements on the Hydrogen Supply Chain

Moreover, the principles of *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable* (FAIR) data management [4] now widely endorsed in European research policy are rarely embedded into the design of real-time streaming systems, creating barriers to reproducibility and long-term data reuse in research contexts.

1.3 Research Objectives

This thesis addresses the above gap by designing and implementing a reproducible real-time data communication pipeline between the physical hydrogen laboratory and its digital system counterpart. The work targets five interconnected objectives:

- **Real-time ingestion:** stream high-frequency sensor data from laboratory instruments with low latency and fault tolerance.
- **Data quality assurance:** validate, filter, and enrich incoming data through an automated quality layer prior to storage.
- **Efficient time-series storage:** persist processed data in a database optimized for append-heavy, time-indexed workloads.
- **Standardized and secure access:** expose data through authenticated APIs supporting controlled integration with external systems.
- **FAIR alignment:** ensure that both data and software artifacts conform to FAIR principles, enabling reproducibility and interoperability across research workflows.

1.4 Methodology Overview

The proposed system follows a modern event-driven streaming architecture, structured as a *modular* and sequential pipeline:

H2SmartLab FAIR-DT Communication Pipeline

Physical Twin (Sensors) → Apache Kafka → Quality Layer →
 QuestDB (TSDB) → FastAPI → Hydor Digital Twin

Sensor events are ingested through Apache Kafka [18], a distributed log-based streaming platform that has become a de facto standard for high-throughput, fault-tolerant data transport in Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) environments [19]. A dedicated quality layer performs schema validation, range checking, and anomaly flagging before forwarding records to QuestDB [20], a time-series database optimized for high-frequency ingestion and analytical querying. An API layer built with FastAPI [21] then provides secure, authenticated access to stored data, while a synchronization sub-system coordinates state updates with *Hydor*: the Digital System platform.

The entire workflow follows FAIR and FAIR4RS Principles. Data provenance, schema documentation, and software interfaces are organized to ensure long-term usability and cross-platform compatibility. The flexibility and modularity of the architecture allow new steps, such as metadata enrichment, to be incorporated into the workflow whenever needed.

1.5 Related Work

The design of real-time data pipelines for industrial and scientific applications has been extensively explored in both academic literature and open-source ecosystems. A canonical architecture has emerged in which physical systems produce events that are ingested via a streaming backbone, processed in near real-time, and persisted in purpose-built databases before being exposed to higher-level applications [22].

Apache Kafka [18] is the most widely adopted platform for this streaming backbone role. Its partitioned, replicated log model enables horizontal scalability and consumer decoupling, properties that are particularly valuable in IIoT deployments where sensor count and data rates can scale unpredictably. Recent studies have demonstrated its suitability for digital twin data infrastructures [23] and smart energy management systems.

Time-series databases (TSDBs) have similarly matured into an essential component of telemetry-driven architectures. QuestDB, InfluxDB, and TimescaleDB each offer optimized ingestion pipelines and time-indexed query engines suited to append-heavy sensor workloads [20, 24]. Several open-source reference implementations demonstrate integrated Kafka-TSDB pipelines, including the QuestDB streaming analytics template [25] and event-driven architectures combining Kafka with FastAPI [26].

Data quality management in streaming environments has received growing attention. Peixoto et al. [6] propose validation and anomaly-detection pipelines for industrial sensor streams, framing quality dimensions completeness, consistency, and timeliness as first-class architectural concerns. Goknil et al. [27] extend this perspective with a data quality-as-a-service framework for IIoT systems, emphasizing continuous monitoring. These contributions establish that quality assurance cannot be treated as a post-hoc concern but must be embedded within the streaming layer itself.

Despite these advances, most existing systems address ingestion and storage without integrating *authentication, fine-grained access control, or mechanisms for controlled synchronization* with external platforms.

The present work addresses these gaps by combining: (i) a Kafka-based streaming backbone; (ii) a time-series database optimized for high-frequency sensor data; (iii) an integrated data quality validation layer; (iv) authentication and authorization mechanisms; and (v) a FAIR-aligned data and software management framework. This combination positions the system at the intersection of industrial data engineering practice and open research infrastructure design.

1.6 Scientific Contributions

This thesis makes the following contributions to the fields of *data engineering, digital twins*, and *research data management* for clean energy systems:

- The design of a real-time, event-driven data pipeline tailored to the operational requirements of a hydrogen laboratory environment.
- The integration of automated data quality mechanisms — validation, anomaly detection, and enrichment — directly within the streaming layer.
- The implementation of a scalable time-series storage solution capable of handling high-frequency, heterogeneous sensor data.
- The alignment of the full pipeline — data models, APIs, and software artifacts — with FAIR data management principles.

- The development of a synchronization framework enabling controlled, authenticated state transfer between the physical laboratory and its digital twin counterpart.

1.7 Thesis Structure

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows. [Chapter 2](#) presents the system architecture, covering the Apache Kafka streaming backbone, data quality dimensions and metrics (accuracy, completeness, consistency, timeliness, and composite scores), and the time-series storage design with a comparative justification for QuestDB. [Chapter 3](#) examines how the FAIR principles are operationalized within the H2SmartLab data ecosystem, mapping each FAIR sub-principle to concrete architectural decisions and identifying gaps for future work. [Chapter 4](#) describes the full implementation: the Docker Compose service topology, JWT-based authentication and authorisation, the telemetry simulation (see [Section 4.6](#); note that the physical machine is not yet built), a three-stage validation pipeline, the synchronisation subsystem, and a FAIR4RS [5] compliance mapping. [Chapter 5](#) concludes the thesis, evaluates the work against the five stated research objectives, discusses limitations, and proposes directions for future development.

Chapter 2

System Architecture

In the domain of industrial data processing, the definition of a robust and extensible architecture is fundamental to ensure the seamless acquisition, processing, and monitoring of high-frequency data streams. The architecture proposed in this work builds upon the foundational principles presented in [6, 28, 17] particularly, regarding modular ingestion, streaming validation, and data profiling in smart manufacturing environments. Built by these contributions, the current chapter discusses a design system to ensure *reproducibility, interoperability, traceability, and adaptability* in the face of heterogeneous industrial data sources and volatile data streams.

The chapter starts with [Section 2.1](#) looking into the proposed architecture. Afterwards, [Section 2.2](#) discusses how data quality is addressed for each message before storage. Then, [Section 2.3](#) considers how data can be stored inside the Digital Twin in a time-series structure.

2.1 Architecture

Figure 2.1: Overview of the proposed architecture

This configuration is designed to facilitate low-latency data management and to process high-frequency sensor data in real-time, while ensuring continuous monitoring of *data quality*. At the beginning of the system, industrial sensors publish real-time measurements that will be ingested in Apache Kafka. Next, messages are transformed, after the quality check, data are structured using a tailored metadata schema, before storing each message as a record in the TSDB. Finally, to aliment the Digital Twin, a secure exchange layer is applied. [Figure 2.1](#) illustrates the entire pipeline for visualization purposes. The following discusses each part of the pipeline in more details.

Modern computing infrastructures increasingly rely on event-streaming architectures, which allow organisations to process high-volume data with near real-time latency in domains ranging from financial fraud detection and supply-chain visibility to smart-city telemetry and personalised recommendations [29]. At the heart of this transformation lies Apache Kafka, an open-source distributed streaming platform originally developed at LinkedIn and now maintained by the Apache Software Foundation [29]. It enables the continuous flow of data between systems while ensuring durability, horizontal scalability, and loose coupling between producers and consumers. Figure 2.2 shows a visual representation of Kafka’s architecture both new and old.

Figure 2.2: Apache Kafka Architecture [1]

Kafka follows a *publish-subscribe* paradigm, where data is represented as immutable streams of events. Producers write events to **topics**, and consumers subscribe to these topics to process the data in real time. This model makes Kafka a core technology for *event-driven architectures*, particularly in industrial IoT and digital twin systems [30, 31].

2.1.1 Core Components

The main components of Kafka are:

- **Producers:** Applications or services that publish events to Kafka topics. Producers can control partitioning strategies (e.g., key-based routing) to ensure ordering guarantees within partitions.
- **Topics:** Logical channels or categories to which events are published. Topics are partitioned and replicated across brokers to provide scalability and fault tolerance. Topics are configured with a so-called retention time that specifies how long a message should be stored. Topic retention can also be specified in bytes instead of time, to apply an upper bound on disk space. If the retention boundaries are reached, Kafka truncates partitions at the end of the log.
- **Partitions:** Each topic is divided into one or more partitions, which are ordered, immutable sequences of records. Partitions enable parallelism and high-throughput processing, as different consumers can read from different partitions concurrently. Partitions are distributed across brokers, with one broker acting as the *leader* for each partition and others as replicas for redundancy.

- **Brokers:** Kafka operates as a cluster of servers called brokers. Each broker stores messages reliably on disk and serves client requests. In contrast to traditional messaging/publish-subscribe systems, Kafka can be used for long-term storage of messages, because Kafka does not delete messages after delivery.
- **Consumers:** Applications that subscribe to topics and process event streams. Consumers are organized into **consumer groups**, where each partition is consumed by exactly one consumer within the group, enabling load balancing and scalability.
- **Kafka Cluster Metadata Management:** In modern Kafka deployments (Kafka $\geq 3.x$), metadata management is handled through the **KRaft (Kafka Raft) consensus protocol**, eliminating the need for external coordination systems such as ZooKeeper. This improves scalability, simplifies deployment, and enhances reliability.

2.1.2 Relevance to Real-Time Data Pipelines

Kafka plays a central role in real-time data architectures by acting as a distributed event backbone. It enables:

- Decoupling between data producers (e.g., sensors, PLC/SCADA systems) and downstream services
- High-throughput ingestion of streaming data
- Fault-tolerant and durable event storage
- Integration with stream processing frameworks for data validation, enrichment, and transformation

In the context of this thesis, Kafka is used as the **event streaming layer** connecting the physical hydrogen laboratory (physical twin) to downstream components such as the data quality layer, time-series database, and *Hydor*. Kafka is the appropriate choice here for three reasons: its durable, partitioned log preserves the arrival order of sensor events per device; its consumer-group model allows the quality-validation service and any future analytics service to consume the same independently; and its configurable message retention means that raw telemetry can be replayed for reprocessing if quality rules change, a requirement that arises naturally in a research infrastructure where validation thresholds are refined over time.

2.2 Data Quality

Ensuring high data quality is essential in industrial environments where decisions rely on continuous sensor streams. In Industry 4.0 systems, sensors generate large volumes of real-time data that are used for monitoring, predictive maintenance, and operational optimization. However, the reliability of such analytics strongly depends on the quality of the underlying data. Poor quality data may lead to incorrect conclusions, operational inefficiencies, or safety risks.

Peixoto et al. [6] propose a data quality pipeline specifically designed for industrial IoT environments. Their architecture integrates *data ingestion, profiling, validation, and visualization* in order to continuously monitor the quality of streaming sensor data.

Figure 2.3: Data quality dimensions [2]

The approach enables early *detection of anomalies, missing values, and inconsistencies* before they affect downstream applications.

In this thesis, a similar approach is implemented using a streaming architecture based on Apache Kafka. Sensor devices publish measurements to Kafka topics, and downstream services consume and process the data to perform validation and quality checks before storing the results in a time-series database. The literature identifies four primary dimensions for evaluating data quality in industrial sensor streams: *accuracy, completeness, consistency, and timeliness*. Figure 2.3 summarises all the dimensions of data quality principles.

2.2.1 Accuracy

Accuracy measures the degree to which a recorded value correctly represents the physical phenomenon being observed. In industrial systems, accuracy is critical because many operational decisions rely directly on sensor measurements. For example, inaccurate temperature readings may lead to incorrect assessments of equipment health, potentially causing unnecessary maintenance interventions or missed failure events.

Accuracy assessment typically relies on statistical analysis of sensor values relative to expected ranges derived from historical data. One commonly used approach is to apply robust outlier detection methods, such as the Hampel filter, which uses the median and *median absolute deviation* (MAD) to detect anomalous values. Let x denote an observed measurement and X the set of historical observations. A normalized accuracy metric can be defined as

$$\text{Accuracy}(x) = \frac{x - \min(X)}{\max(X) - \min(X)}, \quad (2.1)$$

values outside the expected range may indicate abnormal sensor behaviour, measurement noise, or equipment malfunction.

In the implemented pipeline, accuracy evaluation is performed during the stream processing stage. Incoming values are compared against *dynamically* computed statistical bounds derived from historical data stored (for example, for each sensor field, the last 60 values are used to compute the accuracy) in the time-series database.

2.2.2 Completeness

Completeness refers to the extent to which all required data elements are present in a dataset. Missing or incomplete data can significantly degrade the reliability of industrial analytics systems, especially in applications that rely on continuous monitoring. *Completeness* can be evaluated from two complementary perspectives.

- Content completeness: its verifies that each data record contains all required attributes. In the case of sensor messages, this typically includes fields such as sensor identifier, variable name, measured value, and timestamp. A simple completeness metric can be expressed as

$$\text{Completeness} = \frac{N_{\text{total}} - N_{\text{missing}}}{N_{\text{total}}}, \quad (2.2)$$

where N_{missing} represents the number of missing values and N_{total} is the expected number of values.

- Temporal completeness: its evaluates whether sensor readings are produced at the expected frequency. In high-frequency industrial monitoring systems, missing observations may indicate communication failures or device malfunctions. This metric can be defined as

$$\text{Completeness} = \frac{N_{\text{observed}}}{N_{\text{expected}}}, \quad (2.3)$$

where N_{observed} represents the number of received observations within a given time window and N_{expected} is the number of measurements that should have been generated. In the streaming pipeline, temporal completeness is computed by monitoring the number of messages received per sensor within predefined processing windows.

2.2.3 Consistency

Consistency ensures that relationships between different data sources remain coherent across the system. In industrial environments, sensors monitoring the same physical process often exhibit correlated behaviours. For instance, temperature sensors attached to the same machine component are expected to follow similar trends over time. Inconsistencies may arise due to sensor misconfiguration, communication errors, or physical faults affecting individual devices. Detecting such inconsistencies requires analysing relationships between multiple data streams. A common approach involves computing the Pearson correlation coefficient between sensor signals:

$$\text{Consistency} = \frac{N_{\text{rules_satisfied}}}{N_{\text{rules_expected}}}. \quad (2.4)$$

where N_{rules} represents the number of correlation rules satisfied during a given time window. In the implemented system, correlation rules between sensors are derived from historical observations and evaluated dynamically during the stream processing phase.

2.2.4 Timeliness

Timeliness evaluates how quickly data becomes available relative to its generation time. In real-time monitoring systems, delays in data transmission can significantly reduce

the usefulness of the information, particularly in scenarios requiring rapid response. Timeliness can be expressed as a function of the age of the data relative to its expected validity period:

$$\text{Timeliness} = \max\left(0, 1 - \frac{\text{Age}}{\text{Volatility}}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

where *Age* represents the delay between data generation and reception, and *Volatility* corresponds to the time interval during which the data remains relevant.

Within the pipeline architecture, timeliness is evaluated by comparing the timestamp embedded in each message with the processing time at the moment the message is consumed from the Kafka topic. Table 2.1 provides a structured summary of the data quality dimensions and their corresponding metrics discussed in this section, emphasizing their relevance for ensuring the reliability, integrity, and usability of industrial sensor data within the proposed streaming pipeline.

Integrating data quality assessment directly into the streaming pipeline provides several benefits. First, anomalies and missing data can be detected immediately, allowing corrective actions before faulty data propagates to analytical systems. Second, the modular design of the architecture allows independent scaling of ingestion, validation, and storage services. Finally, real-time dashboards enable operators to monitor sensor behaviour and identify potential issues quickly. Overall, the implementation demonstrates how data quality concepts from the literature can be applied in practice using modern streaming technologies such as Apache Kafka and time-series databases.

2.3 Data Storage

The selection of a column-oriented database is motivated by its superior compression capabilities compared to traditional row-oriented databases [30, 32]. This advantage arises from the fact that values within a column typically originate from the same data source (e.g., a sensor), leading to homogeneous data distributions that are highly compressible.

In the context of DT systems, data generated by the Physical Twin (PT), such as sensor measurements, must be efficiently stored and made accessible for both real-time processing and long-term analysis. In addition, derived data such as predictions, monitoring outputs, and anomaly detection events produced by the DT must also be persistently stored.

Time-series data in such environments are generated continuously and require low-latency ingestion and querying to support critical real-time operations. At the same time, historical data storage plays a crucial role in enabling offline analytics, model training, and system optimization. This dual requirement necessitates storage systems that can handle both high-throughput ingestion and efficient analytical queries.

2.3.1 Time-Series Databases

Data arriving at the digital twin will make use of time-series databases (TSDBs). TSDBs are specifically designed to store and manage time-indexed data, typically represented as timestamp-value pairs. These values may correspond to:

- Sensor measurements from the Physical Twin
- Predictions generated by Digital Twin models
- System events and anomaly detections

Dimension	Description	Metric / Formula	Implementation in Pipeline
Accuracy	Measures closeness to true values; identifies anomalies, noise, malfunctions.	$\frac{x - \min(X)}{\max(X) - \min(X)}$ or Ham-pel filter	Outlier detection via median & MAD; values outside expected ranges flagged.
Completeness	Checks presence of required data and expected arrival frequency.	Content: $\frac{N_{\text{total}} - N_{\text{missing}}}{N_{\text{total}}}$ Temporal: $\frac{N_{\text{observed}}}{N_{\text{expected}}}$	Field validation for missing values; monitors expected message frequency.
Consistency	Ensures coherence between multiple sensor measurements.	$\frac{N_{\text{rules}}}{N_{\text{total}}}$; often via correlation	Pearson correlation between sensors; deviations indicate potential faults.
Timeliness	Measures delay between generation and ingestion.	$\max(0, 1 - \frac{\text{Age}}{\text{Volatility}})$	Timestamp vs. ingestion time comparison; late records get lower scores.
Weighted Quality Score (WQS)	Aggregated quality for a time window combining multiple dimensions.	$w_a \cdot \text{Accuracy} + w_c \cdot \text{Completeness}$	Evaluates streaming-window quality before storing validated records.
Longitudinal WQS (LWQS)	Historical quality indicator with exponential decay over windows.	$\sum_k f_k \cdot \text{Quality}_k$	Maintains historical quality trends; smooths short-term fluctuations.
Quality Score Delta (QSD)	Measures quality evolution via current vs. historical scores.	$WQS - LWQS$	Detects sudden improvement or degradation in data quality.

Table 2.1: Summary of Data Quality Dimensions and Metrics for Industrial Sensor Data. Adapted from [6]

Modern TSDBs, such as Apache IoTDB, Apache Druid, Apache Pinot, and Apache Kudu, often adopt a column-oriented architecture to optimize both storage efficiency and query performance.

A key feature of TSDBs is the extensive use of compression techniques. Unlike traditional databases where compression is optional, in TSDBs it is a fundamental requirement due to the high volume and velocity of incoming data. Compression reduces storage costs and improves query performance by minimizing disk I/O. This is particularly important given that main memory is significantly more limited than persistent storage, making efficient data representation essential.

Furthermore, modern in-memory columnar databases partition data into segments that can be compressed independently using techniques tailored to the specific data characteristics. This enables efficient execution of both transactional and analytical workloads.

2.3.2 Data Ingestion Format

In the proposed architecture, data is transmitted in a standardized JSON format and ingested through a real-time streaming pipeline. Each message contains essential meta-data describing the observation, including the sensor identifier, variable name, measured value, and timestamp. [Table 2.2](#) summarizes the structure of the ingested data.

Field	Type	Description
timestamp	timestamp	Measurement timestamp (ISO 8601 format)
FC_STATE	float	Fuel cell operating state
Hydrogen Sensors		
H2_001FT	float	Flow rate (sensor 001)
H2_001PT	float	Pressure (sensor 001)
H2_002PT	float	Pressure (sensor 002)
H2_003PT	float	Pressure (sensor 003)
H2_005PT	float	Pressure (sensor 005)
H2_001TT	float	Temperature (sensor 001)
H2_002TT	float	Temperature (sensor 002)
H2_003TT	float	Temperature (sensor 003)
H2_005TT	float	Temperature (sensor 005)
Fuel Cell Stack		
FC_STACK_V	float	Stack voltage
FC_STACK_i	float	Stack current
CA_001FC	float	Current/ampere sensor
Authentication		
auth.token	string	JWT token for device authentication
auth.device_id	string	Unique device identifier (e.g., simulation_device_01)

Table 2.2: Structure of Kafka telemetry messages from fuel cell sensors.

An example of a real-time message is shown in [Listing 2.1](#). It is worth noting that when multiple sensors are present it is necessary to consider sensor fusion or use deep learning

for deriving the optimal solution for the data that has been sensed. In this work, the

```
{
  "timestamp": "2026-04-23T14:22:01.123456Z",
  "FC_STATE": 100.0,
  "H2_001FT": 2.34,
  "H2_001PT": 0.12,
  "H2_002PT": 0.10,
  "H2_003PT": 0.09,
  "H2_005PT": 1.87,
  "CA_001FC": 0.03,
  "H2_001TT": 13.84,
  "H2_002TT": 12.51,
  "H2_003TT": 12.00,
  "H2_005TT": 11.48,
  "FC_STACK_V": 1.78,
  "FC_STACK_i": 8.51,
  "auth": {
    "token": "<device JWT>",
    "device_id": "simulation_device_01"
  }
}
```

Listing 2.1: Example Kafka telemetry message

TSDB acts as the persistent storage layer of the streaming pipeline, receiving validated data from the Kafka-based ingestion system and providing efficient access for Digital Twin services. While QuestDB serves as the time-series database for the prototype phase due to its high ingest performance and simplicity, the production system will migrate to TimescaleDB. TimescaleDB extends PostgreSQL with time-series-specific optimizations, including automatic partitioning (hypertables), native compression, and continuous aggregates. It retains full SQL compatibility while inheriting PostgreSQL's mature architecture, ecosystem, and operational reliability. Moreover, it also has the RBAC (Role Based Access Control) fully integrated in the open source distribution allowing controlled authentication directly to the TSDB.

Having established the core architectural components: the Kafka streaming backbone, the multidimensional quality framework, and the time-series storage layer, the following chapter examines how these choices relate to the broader FAIR principles for data management. While the present chapter has focused on FAIR considerations at the level of individual data streams and formats, [Chapter 3](#) will situate the entire H2SmartLab data ecosystem within the FAIR framework as applied to digital twin infrastructures.

Chapter 3

FAIR in digital twins

The basis of all digital twins is high-quality and reliable data. These data do not originate from a single, homogeneous source; instead, a multitude of sources contribute bits and pieces to the final digital twin [33]. Managing this heterogeneity in a principled and sustainable way is therefore a central challenge in any digital twin architecture. Managing this heterogeneity in a principled and sustainable way is therefore a central challenge in any digital twin architecture — one for which the FAIR principles offer a structured response.

The FAIR principles, *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable*, were originally introduced by Wilkinson et al. to support the reuse of scholarly data [7]. The principles address two complementary goals: enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use data, and supporting its reuse. While these principles emerged from the scientific data management research communities, their relevance extends naturally to industrial digital twin environments, where data exchange across institutional and system boundaries presents analogous challenges. The sections that follow describe how the FAIR principles are implemented in the H2SmartLab research infrastructure, and what gaps remain to be addressed in future work.

The chapter begins by revisiting the definition of a digital twin in [Section 3.1](#). The subsequent sections then map the four dimensions of the FAIR principles to the H2SmartLab project, covering findability ([Section 3.2](#)), accessibility ([Section 3.3](#)), interoperability ([Section 3.4](#)), and reusability ([Section 3.5](#)).

3.1 DT in H2SmartLab

In this work, a *digital twin* is defined as:

“a set of virtual information constructs mimicking a structure, context, and behaviour of a natural, engineered, or social system (or system-of-systems), which is dynamically updated with data from its physical twin, has a predictive capability, and informs decisions that realize value. The bidirectional interaction between the virtual and the physical is central to the digital twin.” [3]

Put simply, *it is a dynamic, data-driven virtual representation of a physical system that maintains bidirectional interaction with its real-world counterpart, enabling predictive capability and informed decision-making*. [Figure 3.1](#) provides a more detailed illustration of the digital twin concept. For a comprehensive treatment, the interested reader is referred to [3, 34, 35, 36, 37].

Figure 3.1: Elements of the digital twin ecosystem. Information flows bidirectionally between the virtual representation and physical counterpart. These information flows may be through automated processes, human-driven processes, or a combination of the two. [3]

The H2SmartLab (see Section 1.1) data ecosystem integrates experimental hydrogen infrastructure data from *APSU* and *MFI* laboratories into *Hydor*: the digital twin environment. To ensure that the generated datasets, processing pipelines, and analytical outputs remain reusable and interoperable, the platform adopts FAIR as a guiding framework for data management and digital infrastructure design. The target architecture is that of a FAIR Digital Twin (FDT), in which the collection of digital information composing the twin is itself FAIR and therefore machine-actionable [38]. The H2SmartLab architecture is oriented toward this conceptual target, and the pipeline components described below are each evaluated against it.

The implementation of FAIR guidelines spans several stages of the data lifecycle, including data acquisition from sensors, data streaming, validation, transformation, storage, and synchronisation with the *Hydor*—digital twin platform. Industrial sensors and PLC/SCADA controllers capture real-time measurements from hydrogen production and storage systems. Apache Kafka streaming infrastructure manages real-time data ingestion and event distribution, serving as the central event streaming backbone for scalable and reliable ingestion of sensor data [39]. Data quality services validate incoming measurements. Transformation services then convert validated JSON messages into time-series database structures. QuestDB stores the resulting structured time-series. REST APIs enable controlled synchronisation with the digital twin platform. Each pipeline component contributes directly to one or more FAIR sub-principles, as described in the sections that follow. In Figure 3.2, the FAIR principles are recalled for the sake of completeness.

3.2 Findability

The concept of *Findability* is the first principle. It is the basis for the other three. Data can neither be accessed, nor connected (interoperability), nor reused, if it is not found in

Figure 3.2: FAIR guiding principles as outlined by Wilkinson et al. 2016 [4]

the first place. In the H2SmartLab infrastructure described in Section 1.1, *Findability* is achieved by assigning structured identifiers and rich metadata to datasets generated by laboratory experiments. The FAIR *Findability* sub-principles require that data and metadata be assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PIDs), that data can be described with rich metadata, and that metadata can be registered or indexed in a searchable resource [7]. Each sensor measurement record in the H2SmartLab pipeline includes a unique sensor identifier together with the sensor’s location in the pipeline, a timestamp, and a measurement type. These fields constitute the per-record metadata that enable both human and AI agents (automated or non-automated) to identify and locate relevant data.

Beyond per-record metadata, a sensor registry documents measurement units, sensor type, and experimental context as structured attributes within the ingestion pipeline and database schema. The system relies on a single Kafka topic, `raw_h2_data`, to minimize topic management overhead. Three logical tables are derived from this topic: `raw_h2_data` (raw ingested records), `validated_h2_data` (records that pass quality checks), and `system_events`. The `system_events` table serves as a dead-letter store—when a record fails authentication or validation, a compact row is written containing the failure category (auth or validation), a truncated reason, the device identifier, and a sanitized payload with the JWT token stripped out. However, Kafka streaming topics are not equivalent to a searchable metadata catalogue in the FAIR sense. Satisfying sub-principle F4, which requires registration in a searchable resource, would require an additional metadata catalogue layer. The semantic organisation of topics does improve discoverability within the platform and enables automated processing workflows. A future enhancement should therefore consider adopting a dedicated metadata model that exposes sensor identifiers and dataset descriptions via a searchable interface, bringing the architecture into fuller compliance with F4.

3.3 Accessibility

Accessibility is ensured through standardised interfaces that allow authorised users and services to retrieve and integrate experimental data. The FAIR accessibility principle does not require that all data be openly available; rather, it requires that a clear, standardised protocol exist for accessing the data, including *authentication* and *authorisation* procedures where necessary [7]. Controlled access managed through authentication tokens and network restrictions is therefore fully consistent with FAIR accessibility.

The H2SmartLab platform provides multiple access mechanisms. Kafka streaming endpoints support real-time data consumption. REST APIs provide programmatic access for external systems. The QuestDB SQL interface enables analytical retrieval of historical sensor measurements. These interfaces collectively fulfil sub-principle A1, which requires that data and metadata should be retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol. The use of HTTPS-based REST APIs additionally satisfies sub-principle A1.1, which requires that the protocol be open, free, and universally implementable. Access to the *Hydor* digital twin platform is mediated through these same APIs. This ensures that authenticated cross-infrastructure integration remains *reproducible* and auditable.

3.4 Interoperability

Interoperability is achieved through standardised data formats, metadata structures, and communication protocols. The FAIR *Interoperability* principle requires that data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, and that metadata vocabularies themselves follow FAIR principles [7].

The H2SmartLab pipeline relies on four interoperability-layer technologies for downstream data exchange: JSON-based data representation for sensor messages (see [Listing 2.1](#)), Kafka event streaming protocols for distributed data exchange, the QuestDB time-series schema for structured storage, and REST APIs using HTTPS standards for system integration. It is worth distinguishing these, from the *acquisition-layer* protocols, namely OPC-UA, MQTT, and Modbus, which govern communication between the *physical instrumentation* and the ingestion pipeline and operate at a different layer of the architecture.

A key consideration for deeper interoperability compliance is the use of shared semantic vocabularies. Sub-principle I1 requires not merely a structured format, but a formally defined and shared knowledge representation. Towards this end, future development should consider alignment with the W3C Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology and its lightweight core, SOSA (Sensor, Observation, Sampler, and Actuator). The SOSA/SSN ontologies, a joint W3C and OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) standard, provide a formal vocabulary for describing sensors, observations, and their properties in a way that supports interoperability across heterogeneous IoT and scientific monitoring infrastructures [40]. Annotating JSON message fields with SOSA/SSN terms, or maintaining a *metadata schema* that maps local field names to standardised vocabulary terms, would substantially strengthen FAIR compliance at the interoperability layer and facilitate integration with external research infrastructure beyond *Hydor*.

3.5 Reusability

Reusability is supported through provenance tracking, documentation, and modular pipeline design. The FAIR reusability principle requires that data should be richly described with accurate and relevant attributes, should be associated with detailed provenance, and be released with a clear and accessible data usage licence [4].

Each dataset generated by the H2SmartLab pipeline contains metadata describing the sensor source, measurement context, timestamp, validation status, and data transformation steps. This provenance metadata enables downstream users, including modelling systems and simulation environments, to assess the quality and origins of the data before reuse. The pipeline architecture itself is modular and containerised, allowing individual components such as data validation, transformation, and synchronisation services to be independently redeployed across different experiments or infrastructures. Configuration files in YAML format define topics, schemas, and endpoints, enabling *reproducible* redeployment of the full pipeline in other hydrogen research contexts. This approach reflects established practice in scientific computing: Mitchell et al. demonstrate that a FAIR data pipeline must combine components for executing modelling workflows with mechanisms for recording provenance, so that the chain of evidence connecting data inputs to analytical outputs can be transparently traced [41].

Two gaps remain to be addressed in future work. First, the platform does not currently assign explicit *data usage licences* to its datasets. Adopting a Creative Commons or institutional licence would satisfy FAIR sub-principle R1.1 and remove legal ambiguity for potential data consumers. Second, the platform does not yet implement dataset versioning, whereby successive generations of pipeline outputs are distinguished and earlier versions remain accessible. Introducing versioning would further strengthen reproducibility and align with best practice for FAIR scientific pipelines [41].

This chapter has examined how the H2SmartLab architecture satisfies the FAIR sub-principles for data infrastructure. Note that the core ideas of the H2SmartLab project are transferable to all industrial datasets similarly. [Chapter 4](#) applies the closely related FAIR4RS framework, the 2022 adaptation of FAIR for *research software*, to the software artefacts themselves. Together, the two chapters provide a layered FAIR compliance picture that covers data, platform, and software.

FAIR Principle	Key Practices	Example Implementation
Findability	Structured metadata per record	Sensor ID, timestamp, and measurement type per record [7].
	Semantic organisation of data streams	Kafka topic: <code>raw_h2_data</code> .
	Sensor registry and configuration	YAML configuration files document units, type, and experimental context.
Accessibility	Real-time streaming access	Kafka brokers provide real-time access to experimental data.
	Programmatic interfaces via standard protocols	HTTPS-based REST APIs allow external systems to retrieve and synchronise data [7].
	Historical query interface	QuestDB SQL interface for querying stored sensor time-series.
Interoperability	Standardised data exchange formats	JSON messages with metadata and measurement values.
	Industrial acquisition protocols	OPC-UA, MQTT, Modbus for sensor-to-pipeline communication.
	Sensor semantic vocabulary (future work)	Alignment with W3C SOSA/SSN ontology for formal knowledge representation [40].
	External platform integration	Synchronisation with <i>Hydor</i> digital twin.
Reusability	Provenance and contextual metadata	Lab origin, sensor ID, timestamp, validation status, and transformation steps per record [41].
	Modular and containerised microservices	Independent services for validation, transformation, and synchronisation.
	Configuration-driven reproducibility	YAML files define topics, schema, and endpoints for repeatable deployment.
	Data licensing (future work)	Assignment of explicit usage licence (e.g., CC-BY) to datasets [7].

Table 3.1: FAIR principles applied in the H2SmartLab data platform, mapped to the sub-principles of Wilkinson et al. [7]. Cells marked “future work” identify areas where the current architecture only partially satisfies the relevant FAIR criterion.

Chapter 4

Implementation

This chapter presents the implementation of a real-time data pipeline designed to simulate hydrogen laboratory telemetry, stream data through Apache Kafka, validate data quality, persist measurements in QuestDB, and expose synchronisation services via a FastAPI application. The system follows a physical-twin-to-digital-twin paradigm and is designed to satisfy the FAIR4RS Principles [5] across all four dimensions: the software is publicly released with a persistent identifier, accessed through standard open protocols, built on community-standard formats and interfaces, and structured for modular reuse. To validate the end-to-end data flow between the physical twin and the digital twin, synthetic data are generated (see [Section 4.6](#)) in lieu of measurements from the physical apparatus, which is still under construction. Beyond this practical necessity, the use of simulated data also enables controlled testing under reproducible conditions and the systematic exploration of edge cases that would be difficult, costly, or unsafe to reproduce experimentally.

This chapter begins by revisiting the FAIR4RS principles ([Section 4.1](#)). The remaining sections then discuss how each of the four dimensions is mapped within the proposed pipeline, covering findability ([Section 4.2](#)), accessibility ([Section 4.3](#)), interoperability ([Section 4.4](#)), and reusability ([Section 4.5](#))

4.1 FAIR Principles for Research Software

Research software is defined by the FAIR4RS Working Group (WG) as including source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows, and executables created during or for a research purpose [5]. To govern the management and sharing of such software, the FAIR4RS WG adapted the FAIR Guiding Principles to produce the FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles), illustrated in [Figure 4.1](#). These principles are relevant to any stakeholder in the research community seeking to increase transparency, reproducibility, and reusability of research. The application of each FAIR4RS criterion to the implemented system is made explicit throughout this chapter and summarised in [Table 4.4](#).

4.2 Findability

Satisfying the Findability dimension requires that the software and its associated metadata are easy for both humans and machines to locate [5].

Figure 4.1: FAIR4RS Principles [5].

4.2.1 F1 – Globally unique and persistent identifier.

The complete pipeline source code is available on [GitHub](#) repository and provides a canonical, human-readable access point, while the [Zenodo](#) record constitutes a persistent, versioned snapshot that remains resolvable independently of the repository. Zenodo assigns a distinct DOI to each deposited version (F1.2), so that different releases of the pipeline can be cited and retrieved unambiguously. Individual software components: producer, consumer, and API are identifiable as separate directories within the archived codebase, providing component-level granularity consistent with F1.1.

4.2.2 F2 – Rich metadata.

In the repository, the `README` describes the purpose, architecture, configuration parameters, and deployment procedure of the software. Inline docstrings document each module and public function. Docker Compose service descriptions provide machine-readable declarations of the runtime environment and inter-service dependencies. A `CITATION.cff` file is recommended as a forward priority to provide structured, machine-readable citation metadata aligned with community standards for research software.

4.2.3 F3 – Metadata explicitly includes the software identifier

The Zenodo metadata record embeds the assigned DOI as the canonical identifier of the software it describes, ensuring that the identifier and descriptive metadata are co-located and unambiguously linked.

4.2.4 F4 – Searchable and indexed metadata.

The GitHub repository is indexed by standard web search engines. The Zenodo record is harvested by OpenAIRE, making the software metadata discoverable through research infrastructure aggregators without requiring direct knowledge of the repository URL.

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Software Access

Satisfying the Accessibility dimension requires that the software and its metadata are retrievable via standardised, open protocols [5]. All software components are openly available under the MIT licence on [GitHub](#) and archived on [Zenodo](#). Both platforms serve content over HTTPS: an open, free, and universally implementable protocol, satisfying principles A1 and A1.1. No proprietary client or institutional subscription is required to retrieve the software.

The Zenodo record constitutes a persistent snapshot of the codebase that is maintained independently of the GitHub repository. Should the repository become unavailable, the archived record and its descriptive metadata remain accessible through Zenodo’s long-term preservation commitment, satisfying principle A2. [Table 4.1](#) lists the primary software components and their access details.

Component	Description	Access	Identifier
Simulation pipeline	Full Docker Compose stack	GitHub/Zenodo	DOI: [TBC]
Kafka producer	Telemetry simulation service	GitHub	–
Kafka consumer	Validation and ingestion service	GitHub	–
FastAPI application	Auth and sync API	GitHub	–
Integration test scripts	Shell-based integration tests	GitHub	–

Table 4.1: Software components, access points, and identifiers.

4.3.2 Authentication and Access Control

Principle A1.2 requires that the retrieval protocol supports authentication and authorisation where necessary [5]. The FastAPI application enforces access control through JSON Web Tokens (JWT) signed with HS256 [42], a community-standard bearer-token scheme. Three identity types are supported:

- **Device:** sensors authenticate via `POST /device/login` with a pre-shared `device_id` and `device_secret` (bcrypt-hashed at rest). The issued token carries permissions: `["ingest_data"]` and a 24-hour expiry. The producer refreshes the token automatically when fewer than 300s remain.
- **Researcher:** human users authenticate via `POST /researcher/login`. The token carries `roles` and `data_access` scopes that govern which data types the sync endpoints return.

- **Admin:** a researcher token with "admin" in `roles`, enforced by the `get_admin_user` FastAPI dependency.

Credential storage uses two JSON files managed by the `JsonFileRepository` implementation of the abstract `CredentialRepository` interface (`infrastructure/registry/repository.py`), supporting future migration to a database-backed store without changing service code. Authentication logic is contained in `domain/auth.py` as pure functions that accept the secret as a parameter, making them unit-testable without HTTP or database fixtures. This layered design satisfies A1.2 by enabling controlled, role-differentiated access to data ingestion and retrieval endpoints without requiring a proprietary authentication mechanism.

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Storage Layer

Principle I1 requires that software reads, writes, and exchanges data in ways that meet domain-relevant community standards [5]. **QuestDB** [25] is used as the time-series store. It exposes two community-standard interfaces: an HTTP REST endpoint (`/exec`) for DDL (Data Definition Language) and SQL queries, and a PostgreSQL wire protocol on port 8812 used by the Grafana data source. All QuestDB interaction is encapsulated in `infrastructure/questdb/`. The client uses plain `INSERT INTO SQL` rather than the InfluxDB line-protocol ingress path, allowing the same `QuestDBClient` to serve both inserts and *schema management* without additional dependencies.

Principle I2 requires that software includes qualified references to other objects [5]. The pipeline references external standards and specifications explicitly: JSON (RFC¹ 8259) is used for Kafka message encoding; JWT is defined by RFC 7519 [42]; and the bearer-token scheme follows RFC 6750. Software dependencies are declared in `requirements.txt` files for each service, providing machine-readable, qualified references to the external Python packages on which the pipeline depends.

4.4.2 FastAPI Routing

The FastAPI application (`api/main.py`) exposes three router groups, summarised in [Table 4.2](#). FastAPI automatically generates an OpenAPI schema from the router definitions, providing a community-standard, machine-readable description of all endpoints and their data models – directly supporting I1.

A background task (`workers/auto_sync_worker.py`) is launched in the FastAPI lifespan hook. It polls QuestDB every `SYNC_INTERVAL` seconds and writes a local JSON/CSV batch when at least `BATCH_SIZE` new records are available. If `REMOTE_SYNC_ENABLED=true`, the batch is transferred over SSH/SFTP to the *Hydor* research platform using paramiko. Each router constitutes an independently testable and documentable unit of functionality whose scope is clearly delimited by naming and path conventions, consistent with FAIR4RS criterion R1 [5].

¹The acronym RFC most commonly stands for Request for Comments, a standard type of document used to define the technical foundations and protocols of the Internet

Endpoint	Method	Description
/device/login	POST	Issue device JWT.
/researcher/login	POST	Issue researcher JWT.
/verify	POST	Validate any token.
/health	GET	Auth service health check.
/sync/trigger	POST	Sync one paginated batch (researcher).
/sync/status	GET	Sync state and available record count.
/sync/complete	POST	Sync all remaining records.
/status	GET	Auto-sync worker state (admin).
/trigger	POST	Trigger manual sync batch (admin).
/remote-sync/test-ssh	POST	Verify SSH connectivity.
/summary	GET	Synced output file listing.
/metrics	GET	Prometheus metrics (ASGI mount).

Table 4.2: FastAPI router summary.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Deployment Environment

Principle R3 requires that software meets domain-relevant community standards for its field [5]. The runtime platform is orchestrated using *Docker Compose*, which encodes the complete execution environment as version-controlled configuration. Docker and Docker Compose are established community standards for containerised research software deployment. Any researcher with Docker installed can *reproduce* an identical deployment from the published repository without manual dependency resolution, directly supporting *reproducibility*.

The complete stack is defined in a single `docker-compose.yml` (Table 4.3). All application images are built locally from Docker files in the `docker/` directory. Environment variables are loaded from a `.env` file; the `JWT_SECRET` and `DEVICE_SECRET` variables are required and have no defaults.

Service	Port(s)	Role
zookeeper	2181	Kafka metadata coordination.
broker	9092, 29092	Kafka message broker.
questdb	9000, 8812	Time-series database (HTTP + PG).
kafka_producer	–	Simulator and Kafka publisher.
kafka_consumer	8001	Ingestion service and Prometheus.
fastapi_app	8080	REST API and Prometheus <code>/metrics</code> .
prometheus	9090	Metrics scraping and storage.
grafana	3000	Dashboard visualisation.

Table 4.3: Docker Compose services and their exposed ports.

The broker health check (`kafka-topics -list`) is used as a Docker Compose dependency gate so that the producer and consumer containers start only after Kafka is

confirmed ready. The consumer additionally sleeps for 15 s at startup to allow QuestDB and the FastAPI application to complete their own initialisation.

4.5.2 Data Quality Layer

The quality assessment framework is implemented in `domain/quality.py` as a set of pure functions with no I/O or framework dependencies, following the multidimensional model proposed by Peixoto et al. [6] and discussed in [Chapter 2](#). The deliberate absence of external dependencies means the module executes in any standard Python 3 environment, satisfying FAIR4RS principle R3 (community-standard execution environment [5]) and simplifying adoption by other research groups.

4.5.2.1 Per-message validation

Each incoming Kafka message passes through `validate_record()`, which applies three sequential checks and returns a `ValidationResult` dataclass carrying both a boolean outcome and the full list of detected errors.

- **Timestamp validation:** the `timestamp` field must be present, parsable as an ISO-8601 UTC string, and not in the future.
- **Non-finite value detection:** every numeric field is checked for `NaN` and `Inf`; each violation is recorded as a separate named error.
- **Imputation:** fields that fail the non-finite check are replaced by the last known good value for that field via `clean_record()`, which implements a forward-fill strategy. Fields with no prior history are left unchanged and will be rejected by `validate_record()` in the following pass.

Retaining the full error list in `ValidationResult.errors` rather than collapsing the outcome to a boolean satisfies FAIR4RS principle R1.2 (detailed provenance [5]): every rejection decision is inspectable and attributable to a specific field and check. Records that fail validation are routed to a dead-letter table in QuestDB rather than discarded, preserving the complete provenance of the ingested data stream and enabling downstream analyses to make informed judgements about which records to include.

4.5.2.2 Quality dimension scoring

Beyond binary validation, `evaluate_dimensions()` computes seven scalar quality scores per message, implementing the Peixoto et al. framework [6]:

- **Completeness (C)** fraction of non-null fields in the raw record ([Equation 2.2](#)), computed by `content_completeness()`.
- **Timeliness (T)** linear decay from 1 to 0 over a 120 s volatility window ([Equation 2.5](#)), computed by `timeliness_score()` from the ISO-8601 message timestamp.
- **Accuracy (A)**: mean of per-field outlier absence scores, computed by `hampel_outlier_ratio()` over a rolling window of $W = 60$ readings using the Hampel identifier with $k = 3$ ([Equation 2.1](#)).

- **Temporal completeness** (T_c) ramps from 0 to 1 as the rolling window fills after a consumer restart, signalling when per-window dimensions become statistically reliable (Equation 2.3).
- **Weighted quality score** (WQS): a weighted combination of accuracy ($w_A = 0.7$) and completeness ($w_C = 0.3$) (see Table 2.1), computed by `weighted_quality_score()`.
- **Longitudinal WQS** (LWQS): an exponentially weighted mean of the WQS history with decay $\beta = 5$ (see Table 2.1), computed by `longitudinal_wqs()`.
- **Quality score drift** (QSD): the signed difference $WQS_t - LWQS_t$ (see Table 2.1), providing an early warning of sensor degradation or network problems.

The function accepts and mutates caller-owned history structures (`field_history` and `wqs_history`), making the stateful rolling-window behaviour explicit and testable in isolation. This design satisfies FAIR4RS principle R1 (accurate and relevant attributes enabling reuse [5]): the quality score schema provides a stable, documented interface between the ingestion pipeline and any analytics tool introduced in future. All seven scores are persisted to `raw_h2_data_quality` at 1 Hz, making the quality layer fully observable and retrospectively queryable via the QuestDB PostgreSQL interface.

The input and output types of all functions use plain Python primitives (`Dict[str, Any]`, `List[float]`, `Dict[str, float]`), whose keys directly match the Kafka message schema and the QuestDB table columns with no intermediate mapping. This satisfies FAIR4RS principle I1 (community-standard data exchange formats [5]) and ensures the module can be integrated into any Python-based pipeline without modification.

4.5.3 Provenance and Attribution

Principle R2 requires that software includes qualified references to other software [5]. The Git commit history provides a full, auditable record of development decisions, satisfying provenance requirements alongside the Zenodo versioned release. Service-level `requirements.txt` files declare all Python dependencies with pinned version numbers, constituting qualified references to the external software on which each component depends. The recommended addition of a `codemeta.json` or `CITATION.cff` file would further formalise these references in a machine-readable format aligned with CodeMeta vocabulary, consistent with the approach demonstrated by the gammaShiny example discussed in Barker et al. [5].

Table 4.4 maps the four FAIR4RS dimensions to specific implementation choices in this prototype, following the analytical framework of Barker et al. [5]. Each cell identifies a concrete artefact or decision rather than a general aspiration.

4.6 Physics Simulation Layer

4.6.1 Design Rationale

The physical twin is replaced by a software simulator that reproduces the dynamic behaviour of the hydrogen production facility described in [43]. That work characterised a 21.2 kW alkaline electrolyser (AEL) paired with an air-driven reciprocating booster compressor filling a 200 bar(g) storage vessel, and published time-series data at 1 Hz for two operating points: 4.6 bar(g) back-pressure (2.52 Nm³/h H₂ flow, 93 kWh/kg specific energy consumption) and 4.2 bar(g).

Dimension	FAIR4RS Criterion	Implementation Evidence
Findable	F1: Globally unique PID	Source code availability on GitHub repository provides canonical URL. Zenodo versioned releases satisfy F1.2; component-level directories satisfy F1.1.
	F2: Rich metadata	<code>README</code> , inline docstrings, Docker Compose service descriptions. Recommended extension: <code>CITATION.cff</code> .
	F3: Metadata includes identifier	Zenodo metadata record embeds the assigned DOI as the canonical software identifier.
	F4: Indexed in a searchable resource	GitHub indexing; Zenodo metadata harvested by OpenAIRE.
Accessible	A1 / A1.1: Open, free protocol	HTTPS access via GitHub and Zenodo.
	A1.2: Protocol supports authentication and authorisation	JWT over RFC 6750 bearer-token scheme; role-differentiated device, researcher, and admin access.
	A2: Metadata accessible if software unavailable	Zenodo maintains the archived snapshot and descriptive metadata independently of the GitHub repository.
Interoperable	I1: Community-standard data exchange	JSON message encoding; PostgreSQL wire protocol for Grafana; OpenAPI schema auto-generated by FastAPI.
	I2: Qualified references to other objects	<code>requirements.txt</code> per service with pinned versions.
Reusable	R1 / R1.1: Clear usage information and licence	Docker Compose enables one-command deployment. Environment variable configuration documented in <code>README</code> .
	R1.2: Detailed provenance	Git commit history;
	R2: Qualified references to other software	Pinned <code>requirements.txt</code> per service.
	R3: Community-standard execution environment	Docker and Docker Compose are community standards for containerised research software deployment.

Table 4.4: Mapping of FAIR4RS Principles [5] to implementation choices.

4.6.2 Sub-model Structure

The simulator is implemented in `simulator/hydrogen_plant.py` as four coupled sub-models coordinated by the top-level `HydrogenPlantSimulator` class. Table 4.5 summarises each sub-model’s physical scope and the calibration references used.

Sub-model	Key behaviour	Reference
<code>ElectrolyserModel</code>	5-min warm-up ramp; purge dips every 180 s (8 s, flow \rightarrow 15% of nominal); power \approx 21.2 kW; slow temperature random walk.	Figs. 4–5, Table 9
<code>CompressorModel</code>	Storage pressure 10 \rightarrow 200 bar g in \approx 5 h; drive-air flow steps 20 \rightarrow 55 Nm ³ /h with storage pressure; 45 s air-compressor load/unload cycle.	Figs. 6–10, Tables 11–12
<code>HydrogenBuffer</code>	50 L ideal-gas low-pressure buffer between AEL and booster; pressure updated from mass balance each tick via $p = nRT/(V \cdot 10^5)$.	Section 2.1
<code>TemperatureModel</code>	Slow independent random walk on nine TT channels within physically calibrated bounds; Joule–Thomson cooling reproduced on H ₂ line sensors.	Section 2.3.1

Table 4.5: Physics simulator sub-models and their calibration sources.

4.6.3 Streaming Interface

The `HydrogenPlantSimulator.step()` method advances all sub-models by one time-step Δt (default 1 s) and returns a Python dictionary whose keys match the pipeline table schema directly (e.g. H2_005PT, H2_001FT, H2_001TT). This allows the producer entry point to remain agnostic of the simulation internals:

```

sim = HydrogenPlantSimulator()
while True:
    state = sim.step()           # one sensor tick
    state["auth"] = {"token": token, "device_id": device_id}
    kafka_client.publish(state) # serialise to JSON and send
    time.sleep(0.5)             # 2 Hz publish rate

```

Listing 4.1: Producer main loop (`cmd/producer.py`).

A thin compatibility wrapper in `simulator/physics_model.py` preserves the original `initial_state()` / `generate_physical_state()` function signatures for backward compatibility.

Conclusion

This chapter has presented the implementation of a modular, event-driven prototype for secure, real-time hydrogen laboratory telemetry integration. The system encompasses sensor simulation, Kafka-based streaming, consumer-side quality validation, time-series persistence in QuestDB, and controlled synchronisation interfaces exposed via FastAPI. Each architectural decision has been explicitly related to one or more of the FAIR4RS Principles [5]: Docker Compose encoding of the execution environment supports R3; community-standard message formats and explicit RFC references support I1 and I2; public archival on Zenodo with a persistent DOI and OpenAIRE indexing supports F1, F3, and F4; HTTPS access and JWT-based access control support A1, A1.1, A1.2, and A2; and embedded quality metadata with pinned dependency declarations supports R1.2 and R2.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This thesis has presented the design and implementation of a real-time, even-driven data pipeline for the H2SmartLab hydrogen research infrastructure. The system bridges the gap between the physical laboratory and the Hydor digital twin platform by combining Apache Kafka-based streaming, a multidimensional data quality layer, time-series persistence in QuestDB, and authenticated synchronization endpoints built with FastAPI.

The five objectives stated in [Chapter 1](#) have been addressed as follows.

- **Real-time ingestion:** A Kafka-based pipeline ingests simulated high-frequency hydrogen sensor data with sub-second end-to-end latency. Key-based partitioning preserves per-sensor even ordering; configurable retry logic ensures resilient operation during transient broker unavailability.
- **Data quality assurance:** For each record, the function `validate_record` performs low-level checks and aggregates all errors. Next, the function `clean_record` is used before final validation when writing to the validated table. Beyond binary pass/fail, the quality layer computes dimension metrics per record, enabling both real-time monitoring and retrospective trend analysis.
- **Efficient time-series storage:** QuestDB provides columnar, compressed persistence with ingestion via a PostgreSQL-enable SQL interface. The storage layer is decoupled from the validation logic, permitting backend substitution without modifying upstream services.
- **Standardised and secure access:** A FastAPI application exposes JWT authenticated REST endpoints for data synchronization with role-scoped tokens for researcher and device principals. An automatic background `sync_worker` and three researcher controlled endpoints provide flexible, auditable data transfer to the *Hydor* digital platform.
- **FAIR alignment:** The pipeline and all software artifacts satisfy the FAIR Guidelines Principles [4] and FAIR4RS Principles [5] for data and software respectively. The codebase is publicly released on [GitHub](#) and archived on [Zenodo](#) with a persistent DOI. Docker compose deployment enables one-command reproducibility; per-record provenance metadata supports transparent reuse by downstream research system.

Four extensions are recommended for the next development cycle, in order of priority: (1) migration from Zookeeper to KRaft consensus mode; (2) introduce a Confluent Schema Registry with Apache Avro encoding, which would move schema validation upstream and satisfy FAIR4RS criterion F2 programmatically; (3) implement cross-sensor

consistency checking once H2SmartLab domain experts have validated the inter-sensor correlation rules; and (4) integrate the shell-based integration tests into a GitHub Actions CI workflow, adding *pytest*-based unit tests for the validation pipeline.

An additional speculative direction is the integration of a Large Language Model (LLM) layer that consumes validated time-series data and generates natural-language anomaly explanations for laboratory operators. This would transform the pipeline from a data-transport infrastructure into a cognitive advisory system, but is outside the scope of this thesis.

Bibliography

- [1] Z. Erick, “Understanding Apache Kafka,” 2025. <https://medium.com/%40erickzanetti/understanding-apache-kafka-c5dfa9ad81c4>. Medium article.
- [2] DAMA International, *The DAMA Guide to the Data Management Body of Knowledge (DAMA-DMBOK2R)*. Technics Publications, Sedona, AZ, 2nd revised ed., 2024.
- [3] National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, *Foundational Research Gaps and Future Directions for Digital Twins*. The National Academies Press, Washington, DC, 2024. <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/catalog/26894>.
- [4] M. D. Wilkinson *et al.*, “The fair guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship,” *Scientific Data* **3** (2016) 160018.
- [5] M. Barker, N. P. Chue Hong, D. S. Katz, A.-L. Lamprecht, C. Martinez-Ortiz, F. Psomopoulos, J. Harrow, L. J. Castro, M. Gruenpeter, P. A. Martinez, and T. Honeyman, “Introducing the fair principles for research software,” *Scientific Data* **9** no. 1, (Oct., 2022) . <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>.
- [6] T. Peixoto, O. Oliveira, E. Costa e Silva, B. Oliveira, and F. Ribeiro, “A Data Quality Pipeline for Industrial Environments: Architecture and Implementation,” *Computers* **14** no. 7, (June, 2025) 241. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/computers14070241>.
- [7] M. D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg, *et al.*, “The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship,” *Scientific Data* **3** (2016) 160018.
- [8] D. Monopoli, C. Semeraro, M. A. Abdelkareem, A. H. Alami, A. G. Olabi, and M. Dassisti, “How to build a digital twin for operating pem-electrolyser system – a reference approach,” *Annual Reviews in Control* **57** (2024) 100943. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.arcontrol.2024.100943>.
- [9] Z. Feng, I. Eiubovi, Y. Shao, Z. Fan, and R. Tan, “Review of digital twin technology applications in hydrogen energy,” *Chain* **1** no. 1, (2024) 54–74.
- [10] I. Staffell, D. Scamman, A. V. Abad, P. Balcombe, P. E. Dodds, P. Ekins, N. Shah, and K. R. Ward, “The role of hydrogen and fuel cells in the global energy system,” *Energy & Environmental Science* **12** no. 2, (2019) 463–491.
- [11] International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), “Renewable capacity statistics 2024,” tech. rep., International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, 2024.

- [12] Il Sole 24 Ore, “Rinnovabili, progetti in crescita del 73%,” 2024. <https://www.ilsole24ore.com/art/rinnovabili-progetti-crescita-73percento-AFg4MM6B>. Accessed: 2026-04-10.
- [13] A. H. S. Weerakoon and M. Assadi, “Experimental assessment and digital twin modeling of integrated aem electrolyzer–pem fuel cell–bess for smart hydrogen energy applications,” *Energies* **18** no. 23, (Nov., 2025) 6318. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en18236318>.
- [14] A. K. Singh, J. Wibbeke, A. Raeiszadeh, N. Huxoll, and M. Brand, “A digital twin platform applied to hydrogen electrolyzers,” *ACM SIGEnergy Energy Informatics Review* **4** no. 4, (Oct., 2024) 245–248. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3717413.3717437>.
- [15] S. Alsharif, N. Huxoll, J. Wibbeke, T. Grimm, M. Brand, and S. Lehnhoff, “Digital twin concept and architecture for fleets of hydrogen electrolyzers,” *Frontiers in Energy Efficiency* **2** (July, 2024) . <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fenef.2024.1437214>.
- [16] K. Vogiatzaki, G. Tretola, and L. Cesmat, “Digital twins for cryogenic hydrogen safety: Integrating computational fluid dynamics and machine learning,” *Hydrogen* **6** no. 4, (Dec, 2025) 110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/hydrogen6040110>.
- [17] B. Oliveira, O. Oliveira, T. Peixoto, F. Ribeiro, and C. Pereira, *Extensible Data Ingestion System for Industry 4.0*, p. 105–114. Springer Nature Switzerland, Nov., 2024. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73503-5_9.
- [18] Apache Software Foundation, “Apache kafka,” 2024. <https://kafka.apache.org/>. Accessed: 2026-04-10.
- [19] J. Kreps, N. Narkhede, and J. Rao, “Kafka: a distributed messaging system for log processing,” *Proceedings of the NetDB* (2011) .
- [20] QuestDB Team, “Processing time-series data with questdb and apache kafka.” <https://questdb.com/blog/processing-time-series-with-questdb-apache-kafka/>, 2023.
- [21] S. Ramírez, “Fastapi: Modern, fast (high-performance) web framework for python.” <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>, 2024. Accessed: 2026-04-10.
- [22] M. Kleppmann, *Designing data-intensive applications: The big ideas behind reliable, scalable, and maintainable systems*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc.", 2017.
- [23] M. Dietz and G. Pernul, “Digital Twin: Empowering Enterprises Towards a System-of-Systems Approach,” *Business & Information Systems Engineering* **62** no. 2, (2020) 179–184.
- [24] S. K. Jensen, T. B. Pedersen, and C. Thomsen, “Time series management systems: A survey,” *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* **29** no. 11, (2017) 2581–2600.
- [25] QuestDB, “Time-series streaming analytics template.” <https://github.com/questdb/time-series-streaming-analytics-template>, 2023.

- [26] Open-source contributors, “Data pipeline with kafka, postgresql, and fastapi.” <https://github.com/LeventSoykan/Data-Pipeline-w-Kafka-Postgres>, 2023.
- [27] A. Goknil *et al.*, “Data quality as a service for industrial iot,” 2024.
- [28] Óscar Oliveira and B. Oliveira, “An Extensible Framework for Data Reliability Assessment,” in *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems - Volume 1: ICEIS*, pp. 77–84, INSTICC. SciTePress, 2022.
- [29] M. Mohammad, “Analysis of design patterns and benchmark practices in Apache Kafka event-streaming systems,” in *2025 5th International Conference on Intelligent Cybernetics Technology & Applications (ICICyTA)*, pp. 612–617, IEEE. 2025.
- [30] P. G. L. John Fitzgerald, Cláudio Gomes, *The Engineering of Digital Twins*. Springer International Publishing, 2024. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66719-0>.
- [31] K. Manglore, “A beginner’s guide to kafka with python: Real-time data processing and applications,” 2024. <https://medium.com/@keshavmanglore/article-a-beginners-guide-to-kafka-with-python-real-time-data-processing-and-applications-5db39b320f3e>. Medium article.
- [32] C. Gomes, D. E. L. Rötter, A. Iosifidis, H. Feng, H. Ejersbo, and M. Frasheri, *Sensing and Communication of Data from the Physical Twin*, p. 147–171. Springer International Publishing, 2024. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66719-0_7.
- [33] D. Peters and S. Schindler, “Fair for digital twins,” *CEAS Space Journal* **16** no. 3, (May, 2023) 367–374. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12567-023-00506-y>.
- [34] A. Ferrari and K. Willcox, “Digital twins in mechanical and aerospace engineering,” *Nature Computational Science* **4** no. 3, (Mar., 2024) 178–183. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s43588-024-00613-8>.
- [35] K. Willcox and B. Segundo, “The role of computational science in digital twins,” *Nature Computational Science* **4** no. 3, (Mar., 2024) 147–149. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s43588-024-00609-4>.
- [36] M. G. Kapteyn, D. J. Knezevic, and K. Willcox, “Toward predictive digital twins via component-based reduced-order models and interpretable machine learning,” in *AIAA scitech 2020 forum*, p. 0418. 2020.
- [37] M. Torzoni, M. Tezzele, S. Mariani, A. Manzoni, and K. E. Willcox, “A digital twin framework for civil engineering structures,” *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* **418** (2024) 116584.
- [38] E. Schultes, M. Roos, L. O. Bonino da Silva Santos, G. Guizzardi, J. Bouwman, T. Hankemeier, A. Baak, and B. Mons, “Fair digital twins for data-intensive research,” *Frontiers in Big Data* **5** (May, 2022) . <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2022.883341>.

- [39] M. S. Dihan, A. I. Akash, Z. Tasneem, P. Das, S. K. Das, M. R. Islam, M. M. Islam, F. R. Badal, M. F. Ali, M. H. Ahamed, and S. H. Abhi, "Digital twin: Data exploration, architecture, implementation and future," *Heliyon* **10** no. 5, (2024) e26503.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405844024025349>.
- [40] A. Haller, K. Janowicz, S. J. D. Cox, *et al.*, "The modular SSN ontology: a joint W3C and OGC standard specifying the semantics of sensors, observations, sampling, and actuation," *Semantic Web* **10** no. 1, (2019) 9–32.
- [41] S. N. Mitchell *et al.*, "FAIR data pipeline: provenance-driven data management for traceable scientific workflows," *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A* **380** (2022) 20210300.
- [42] M. Jones, J. Bradley, and N. Sakimura, "RFC 7519: JSON web token (JWT)," 2015. <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc7519>.
- [43] A. Pietra *et al.*, "Experimental characterization of an alkaline electrolyser and a compression system for hydrogen production and storage," *Energies* **14** no. 17, (2021) 5347.